

Supplementary Material S4: GATE/Geant4 Simulation Parameters (5,000 iterations/scenario)

SCANNER GEOMETRY (GE Discovery MI - clinically validated specifications)

PHANTOM CONFIGURATION (NEMA NU2-2018 Image Quality phantom)

RECONSTRUCTION SCENARIOS (CASToR v3.1.1 validated implementation)

MONTE CARLO PARAMETERS

PRIMARY KPIS COMPUTED

GATE MACRO STRUCTURE (available Zenodo):

SCANNER : GE Discovery MI (LYSO 4×4×20mm, TOF=385ps) PHANTOM : NEMA NU2-2018 (100MBq 18F, 6 spheres) RECON : OSEM(4i20s) vs BSREM($\beta=50$)

Full GATE macros + parameter sweeps: Zenodo DOI:10.5281/zenodo.18745283